

DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES OF PEDAGOGICAL COOPERATION OF FAMILY, NEIGHBORHOOD AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698867>

Abstract. *In the article, the issue of social-pedagogical cooperation of the family, neighborhood and educational institutions in the education of young people in Uzbekistan was studied comparatively and analytically with the experiences of foreign countries, and the research works of our scientists who made a significant contribution to the education and upbringing of young people in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the development of their moral and moral qualities were compared. the results of the study are reflected. Ways to improve the socio-pedagogical cooperation of family, neighborhood and educational institutions, the results of conducted experiments, the results of organized seminar-training, proposals, recommendations and conclusions are highlighted.*

Keywords: *person, education, upbringing, family, neighborhood, educational institution, social, spirituality, enlightenment, cooperation, activity, ability, discipline.*

Introduction

Great reforms are being carried out in all spheres in new Uzbekistan today. The main factor of the ongoing reforms is for the benefit of people. Fundamental reforms are being carried out, including in the field of education. Therefore, the countries of the world recognize the opportunities created in New Uzbekistan for the development of mental, spiritual, educational and physical maturity of young people, for them to acquire knowledge in accordance with the requirements of the time, to acquire professions, to show and further develop their talents and abilities.

The innovative ideas put forward by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his Addresses to the Oliy Majlis, which are creating progressive changes in the history of our modern statehood, have become important in improving the cooperation of the family, neighborhood and educational institutions in raising a mature generation in our country. Today's demand is to educate young people in a national and modern spirit and inculcate them with innovative ideas.

The new version of the Law "On State Policy Regarding Youth" was adopted in order to raise our efforts to educate the young generation in a healthy and well-rounded manner. At the same time, new approaches are being actively introduced to life.

Based on the characteristics of the object of our research, the process of increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the social-pedagogical cooperation of family, neighborhood and educational institutions and this process it is important to what extent the content, form and methods are reflected in scientific research.

Therefore, in order to justify the researched problem and find its scientific solution, we analyzed the pedagogical features and aspects of spiritual educational work in the social cooperation of family, neighborhood and educational institutions in the educational process. First

of all, we researched the analysis based on the scientific research, literature, their execution and implementation.

Today in Uzbekistan, education of a mature generation is the main, priority issue of social, spiritual and educational cooperation of family, neighborhood and educational institution. For this, it is appropriate to highlight the improvement of social cooperation of family, neighborhood and educational institution as an example of spiritual-educational activity, in the process of analysis, to clarify the concept of "spiritual-educational".

One of the factors determining the place and level of our country in the world is spirituality. This has been confirmed in the course of development in the three-thousand-year history of the Uzbek state, and therefore, since the first years of national independence, the issue of spiritual values, their preservation, restoration and transmission to the next generation has become the most urgent issue.

For this purpose, we considered it appropriate to analyze the dictionary meanings of the concepts of "spirituality" and "enlightenment" in order to fully illuminate the basis of the spiritual and educational activities carried out in the social cooperation of the family, neighborhood and educational institutions. Spirituality is an Arabic word that means "a set of meanings" - a set of philosophical, legal, scientific, moral, religious ideas and concepts of people.

All humanity has accumulated life experience in its thousand-year historical development, cooperated with the surrounding nature and existence, and taught the next generation all the information and activities of natural phenomena, life, duties to the Motherland, nation and people, and the formation of a person as a person. Among them, the Uzbek people have been collecting their own set of knowledge for centuries. But national colonialism, which lasted for more than 120 years, had a very negative impact on the development of our national spirituality.

Therefore, since the first years of the national independence of Uzbekistan, the restoration, development and further formation of the unique national spirituality of our people - the set of national meanings - has risen to the level of state policy. "Because each nation's determination of its own spirituality, knowledge of it, and making it part of its intelligence and consciousness by its own will strengthens the nation, strengthens its self-confidence, belief and dignity. Of course, this was contrary to the ruling ideology of the former system. For this reason, the word and concept of "Spirituality" was removed from our language.

The concept of Enlightenment represents action and means to know in Arabic. The activity aimed at developing people's consciousness and culture based on a set of educational, economic, political, philosophical, and religious ideas constitutes the dictionary content of the word "enlightenment". The word enlightenment is one of the central concepts of Sufism. Sufis, who divide science into external (external) and internal (internal) knowledge, accepted enlightenment as "inner science".

In elucidating the essence of social cooperation, it is necessary to elucidate the social pedagogical aspects of the problem. It can be seen from the socio-historical and analytical sources that have studied this field that at the core of social cooperation are personal interests, interpersonal relations and the content of each person's activities, which are manifested in a complex way, and it is a mechanism that forms and develops the joint activities of state and non-state organizations, that is, family, neighborhood and educational institutions.

This encourages us to pedagogically illuminate the issue of interpersonal and family, neighborhood and educational institutions' social-cooperative activities before studying the

methodological aspects of the problem. In the organization of social cooperation, first of all, it is necessary to study the existing conditions of the family, neighborhood and educational institutions. We think that researching the pedagogical mechanism of social cooperation will help define the nature of the problem more clearly.

Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences M. Inomova conducted her doctoral dissertation on the spiritual and moral education of young people in the family. "Family education" is a pedagogical concept, which is the political, legal, moral, aesthetic, religious views of the child with the help of their life activities, lifestyles, and traditions, means the formation of ideas and visions, and represents a consistent process of spiritual influence, aimed at one goal. This reveals that there are wide opportunities for researching the content of family education as a pedagogical process, came to the conclusion that This reveals that there are wide opportunities for researching the content of family education as a pedagogical process.

It is important to prepare girls for family life, to consciously convey to them the true essence of family education in improving the social cooperation of family, neighborhood and educational institutions. "When a girl is over seven years old, neither her father nor her brothers tried to kiss her, because they knew that this would have a negative effect on the upbringing of the girl child because her organism had begun puberty," wrote H. Umirov, a scientist who collected Uzbek folk paintings. Q. Haydarov and M. Khalikov.

The gender characteristic of spiritual education is also reflected in Islamic enlightenment. Mufti Usmankhan Alimov, chairman of the Office of Muslims of Uzbekistan, writes about this. "Women should dress modestly and behave well. This indicates that if Uzbek girls dress and behave on the basis of national education and develop spiritual and moral qualities in them, they will not be subjected to the attacks of "mass culture" coming from the West.

Doctor of political sciences, professor Kahramon Quranbaev, based on the results of his research, the essence of forming spiritual qualities in students and youth is to find in them the skills of self-sacrifice for the benefit of the people and the Motherland, to create conditions for them to realize their opportunities and abilities, and most importantly, to develop social activity in young people. states that it consists of This is valuable in turning the formation of the above qualities into tasks of social-pedagogical cooperation.

From the point of view of our research, the three-tier system of measurement of the criteria, indicators, levels and qualities of students' national upbringing, developed by Mukhammadjon Kuronov, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, is of particular importance. Because patriotism, national pride, culture of inter-ethnic communication, conscientiousness, national manners and national ideological consciousness, based on the practical unity of scientific and folk pedagogy, are qualities directly and indirectly related to the national feeling of a developing person.

As a result of the observations, the following conclusions and suggestions can be made:

Offers:

- It is necessary to carry out regular, continuous social cooperation in each educational institution and neighborhood.
- It is necessary to establish "Parents' Universities" in educational institutions and neighborhoods.
- It is advisable to organize libraries in families and neighborhoods based on the principle that every family is a reader.
- It is necessary to regularly monitor the activity of clubs organized in the neighborhood and educational institutions.

Summary

In short, education is a practical pedagogical process aimed at forming certain physical, mental, moral and spiritual qualities in a person; is a set of measures taken to ensure that a person has the necessary emotions to live in society. Therefore, education is a phenomenon realized on the basis of social cooperation, and it is the most ancient and eternal spiritual value that ensures the formation of a person as a person.

It is important to study the scientific research conducted in the improvement of social cooperation of the family, neighborhood and educational institutions, as well as to study the activities of scientific centers established in foreign countries in this regard. In improving the social cooperation of the family, neighborhood and educational institutions, drawing up a working plan, directing the plan to its execution on the basis of coherence and consistency ensures effective results.

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